

Historical Network Research: Perspectives and Possibilities from the 2025 Conference

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The community around historical network analysis expands its horizons

The community built around social network analysis goes back to 2009. The current book of abstracts is merely one link in a chain of conferences, workshops, and publications that started then and that will go on for the foreseeable future. If in 2009 most of the community was composed mostly of German-speaking historians, in 2025 it is clear that the reach and demography of the community have expanded, evolved and diversified. The 2005 took place in the Global South, and had participants from Mexico to Japan, and from the South of Brazil to Finland. The book you now read is evidence of how historical network analysis is no longer a niche.

As in any conference, the most precious element of this one is its people and the connections they built. Scholars tend to work alone in their own specific field of study and generally lack opportunities and sometimes even institutional infrastructure to build projects based on interdisciplinary cooperation. In this sense, it is common for historians dedicated to Ancient History to just participate in conferences of Ancient History; World War II scholars to just attend seminars dedicated to this topic and so on. Scholar work in the 21st century has followed a trend of insularity and severe specialization, at the same time it has a crisis of funding. If funding and structure can be a problem in Lausanne or Germany, those challenges are even more true to the Global South. In Rio's 2025 HNRC, potential partnerships were discussed among the peers, as well as ways to surpass traditional ways of thinking about space, time and other crucial concepts for historical analysis. The fruits of these discussions might not include big funding projects at first. Nonetheless, joint ventures, publications and other steps that might seem small can be crucial to explore the full potential of Historical Network analysis. As the abstracts and the keynote speakers' intellectual trajectory suggest, the conference counted with intellectual exchange from people from Architecture, History, Computing Linguistics, Data Science, Business Administration among others. In other words, Rio Conference was a crystal-clear evidence on how HNR can be a platform of thinking, a meeting space for experts in different contexts, fields of study, departments, forms of knowledge etc. In other words, HNR has in its fundamental nature the call for transdisciplinary work. And the book you have in hand represents a fraction of what the conference was, but it is also a witness its wonderful potential.

The HNR2025 Conference

The HNR2025 conference was a continuation of the previous work of this community. As such, it is a place where we can observe current trends in our field and identify some of its protagonists. While the previous edition focused on network visualization practices, in 2025 the conference focus was Network Data.

One topic that is mentioned over and over in the HNR meetings relates to data. In fact, issues related to difficulty of gathering data, data quantity, quality, or missing instances, etc. arise in many talks and papers. With the aim of tackling these issues, HNR 2025 proposes to focus on the various questions centered on data and methods related to their use. Thus, HNR 2025 encourages researchers to share their experiences, problems faced in their research, as well as to discuss proposed solutions. We plan one plenary session dedicated to a reflection, by the community as a whole, about a possible data repository or other kinds of collaborative platforms or tools. We also plan a special track and a workshop on using large language models

(LLMs) to extract, transform, and analyze network data. This theme was reflected in particular on the topics and talks of the workshops and keynotes.

As for the 14 papers accepted for this conference, they present a broad overview of what is being done today in historical network analysis. It is important to say that this year's conference held an impressive participation of non-European institutions and scholars (42,85%). Also, 75% of the keynote speakers were Brazilians. The high participation of non-European attendees translated to an impressive diversity of objects of study, as well as innovative and creative perspectives on the Historical Network analysis. The attendees also ranged from PhD candidates to well-established professors, testifying the crystallization of the field and its potential to the future. Considering how the expansion of horizons has been an ongoing worry of the organizers, Rio's conference seems to be successful on that note.

The abstracts encompassed on this book is a small photograph of an ongoing process. But the photographs here range from 17th and 18th century Arabian Peninsula discussing Mysticism during the Islamic Reformation to the pedagogical potential of HNR to High School Students; from how Public and Local History of Cologne is connected to civil initiatives and associations where institutional frameworks are absent to the epistolography of the Middle Ages. The abstracts cannot be thought as the full conference potential or a representation of all builds bridge. But it certainly enlightens us on how far we have fared, and much more we need to go. The challenge identified last year remains: the HNR community still need to build more bridges beyond Western scholar realities.